

ORGANIZATION OF COMPETITIVE VARIETY TESTING OF SELECTED PROMISING POTATO VARIETIES

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Abstract. This article outlines the results of an experiment comparing the newly developed potato variety “Tashkent Ertagisi” with the standard variety “Sante” in an early-stage trial. According to the experimental findings, the phenological observations of the “Tashkent Ertagisi” and standard “Sante” varieties grown in the selection nursery were as follows. In the standard variety, it took 28 days for 75% of the seedlings to emerge, 34 days for tuber formation, and 52 days for flowering. In contrast, the new “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety required only 22 days for 75% seedling germination, 28 days for tuber formation, and 38 days for flowering. Experimental results confirmed that the growth phases of the new “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety developed 18-20 days earlier than those of the standard variety.

Keywords: Potato, early-maturing, early planting period, growth period, seedling germination, tuber formation, flowering, stem height, number of stems, flower, yield.

Introduction. Potatoes are one of the most important, widely cultivated, and strategically significant food, fodder, and industrial crops in global agriculture. Currently, potatoes are grown in over 150 countries worldwide, covering 23.1 million hectares and yielding a total production of 438.9 million tons.

The average potato yield globally is about 18-19 tons per hectare. In recent years, potato cultivation areas have expanded by 4-5 million hectares, and total production has increased by 70-80 million tons. In major potato-producing countries, one of the most pressing challenges is developing new, adaptable, and promising varieties, as well as rapidly multiplying high-quality seed materials to enhance production volume and crop yield.

In our country's potato industry, extensive efforts are being made to develop new, competitive varieties for the global market, as well as to rapidly propagate them and establish an effective seed production system.

The purpose of the research. Based on a comprehensive study of the global potato gene pool, the goal is to develop and introduce into production an early-maturing variety adapted to the soil and climatic conditions of our country, with high marketability and yield characteristics.

The object of the research. Fifteen lines imported from the International Potato Center (CIP), along with five local and five foreign variety samples, serve as the study objects.

The subject of the research is the morphobiological characteristics and complex valuable economic traits of potato collection samples, including high yield potential, early maturity, the number of tubers per plant stem, and the identification of economically significant traits.

Research methods. The experiments were carried out based on the methodologies and recommendations of the All-Russian Research Institute of Potato Farming, the Research Institute of Vegetable crops, Melons, and Potato Crops, and the State Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Testing New Varieties of Agricultural Crops. The statistical analysis of the field experiment results was performed using the B.A. Dospekhov method with the help of Microsoft Excel software.

Experiment results and their discussion. The competitive variety testing of potatoes is a research process conducted to determine the yield potential of potato varieties, their adaptation to growing conditions, and their resistance to diseases and pests.

Competitive variety testing is carried out to test the yield characteristics, stability, and environmental compatibility of new potato varieties in the production of new varieties.

In this case, several potato varieties are tested in an alternative manner (according to germination, flowering, stem height, and yield indicators).

These tests are important for potato farmers, as they help to select the most productive, high-yielding, and disease- and pest-resistant varieties.

Competitive variety testing also plays an important role in the development of new potato varieties.

When potato lines from the International Potato Center (CIP) were planted in a variety selection nursery, the early-ripening, smooth-skinned, compact, high-yielding (L-60) line was selected from the variety samples.

In the conducted experiments, the valuable economic traits of this L-60 line were studied. During this period, regular individual selection work was carried out. It was found that the germination of the seedlings, flowering, and budding in

this isolated line were 20-25 days earlier than the standard “Sante” variety. In the experiments, it was found that the height of plants at the base of this line was 10-12% higher than the standard variety, the number of stems, stem weight, and number of leaves were 13-14% higher relative to the standard, the leaf area was 10-12% higher, the weight of the shoots was 6-7% higher, and the yield was 11-12% higher than the standard variety.

Scientific research was continued on the L-65 line, which was isolated for a comprehensive study of valuable economic traits of potato lines in early and succession period, and a competition was held for the shape, color, yield, taste and other characteristics of potato tubers in early and succession terms. The main economic characteristics and traits were brought to uniformity. On the recommendation of the Scientific Council of the Research Institute of Vegetable Crops, Melons and Potatoes, the L-65 potato line was named “Tashkent Ertagisi” and was transferred to the Center for Testing Agricultural Crop Varieties and the Intellectual Property Agency, and the state variety testing of these varieties was carried out.

The new potato variety was tested in greenhouse conditions and in open field conditions in early and successive terms for the shape, color, yield and other characteristics of its tubers. The main valuable economic characteristics and traits were brought to uniformity.

Since there was no ultra-early variety of potato in the register of the Center for Testing Agricultural Crop Varieties, this variety was studied in comparison with the “Sante” variety.

Seeds of the new potato variety were sown in early terms on March 20 and succession terms on July 20 in a planting scheme of 70×25 cm.

Precocity. In the experiments conducted, when the new variety was studied for its precocity, it took 85 days for the standard “Sante” variety to reach technical maturity, while the new “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety required 65 days and ripened 20 days earlier than the standard variety. The results of phenological observation of the new “Tashkent Ertagisi” and standard “Sante” varieties of potatoes planted in an early period are presented in Table 1.

Table-1

The results of phenological observation of the new “Tashkent Ertagisi” and standard “Sante” varieties of potatoes planted in an early period (in 2020-2021)

Varietal samples	germination, day		From full germination to....., day			
			budding		flowering	
	10%	75%	10%	75%	10%	75%
Sante (st)	15	28	24	34	40	52
Tashkent Ertagisi (L-65)	13	22	20	28	32	38
V%	10	25	26	31	28	36
V%	15	30	25	33	27	35

According to the results of the study, in the standard variety “Sante” 10% of seedlings germinated in 15 days, 75% in 28 days, from full germination to budding 10% in 24 days, 75% in 34 days, from full germination to flowering 10% in 40 days, and 75% in 52 days, while the newly created variety “Tashkent Ertagisi” 10-75% of seedlings germinated in 2-6 days, from full germination to budding 4-6 days, and from full germination to flowering 8-12 days earlier than the standard variety.

The results of the study shows that the coefficient of variation for the standard variety “Sante” and new variety “Tashkent Ertagisi” at the germination of 10% of seedlings was moderately fluctuating in the range of 10-15%, at the germination of 75% of seedlings it was strongly fluctuating in the range of 22-28%, and from the time of full germination to 10-75% budding and flowering, the coefficient of variation was strongly fluctuating in the range of 25-36%. The stem height and number of stems of potato samples planted in the selection nursery at an early stage are presented in Table 2.

Table-2

The biometric measurement results of the potato varieties “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” planted in the selection nursery in an early planting period (in 2020-2021)

Varietal samples	At the full flowering stage				Plant height at the harvesting period		Color of flower
	Stem height		Stem number				
	cm	relative to st, %	piece	relative to st,%	cm	relative to st,%	
Santé (st)	50,0	100,0	2,9	100,0	53,2	100,0	white
Tashkent Ertagisi	54,8	109,6	3,3	113,8	58,5	109,9	white
r=	0,87±0,13						
r=	0,89±0,11						

The experiments showed that the stem height of the standard variety “Sante” was 50.0 cm (100%) during the full flowering period, while in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety it was 54.8 cm, that is 9.6% higher than the standard variety, the number of stems in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety was 13.8% higher than the standard “Sante” variety, and the stem height of the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety during the harvest period was 9.9% higher than the standard variety.

During the period of full flowering of the plant, the correlation between the height of the stem and the number of stems was $r=0.87\pm 0.13$ in the standard variety “Sante”, $r=0.89\pm 0.11$ in the variety “Tashkent Ertagisi”, and the correlation was strong in both varieties.

The indicators of stem weight, number of leaves and leaf surface per plant of potato varieties planted in the selection nursery in an early period, are presented in Table 3.

Table-3

The weight of stems per plant, number of leaves, and leaf surface of potato varieties “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” planted in the selection nursery in an early planting period (in 2020-2021)

Varietal samples	Per plant						Leaf surface
	Stem weight		Number of leaves		Leaf surface		m ² /ha
	g	Relative to st, %	piece	Relative to st, %	dm ²	Relative to st, %	
“Sante”(st)	380	100,0	384	100,0	55,4	100,0	33,7
“Tashkent Ertagisi”	425	111,8	419	109,1	60,2	108,6	34,5

The potato varieties studied in the experiment had different indicators of stem weight per plant, number of leaves, leaf area per plant and per hectare of area. The standard variety “Sante” had a stem weight of 380 g, compared to which this indicator was 11.8% higher in the new variety “Tashkent Ertagisi”, and the number of leaves per plant in the variety “Sante” was 384 pieces, compared to which this indicator was 9.1% higher in the new variety “Tashkent Ertagisi”.

Phenological monitoring and biometric measurement of the “Tashkent Ertagisi” potato variety planted in an early planting period

The leaf surface per plant of the standard “Sante” variety was 55.4 dm², compared to which this indicator was 8.6% higher in the new “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety. Experiments revealed that the leaf surface area per hectare was higher in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety relative to the standard.

The yield results of potato samples planted in the selection nursery in an early period were studied and presented in Table 4.

Table-4

The yield results of the potato varieties “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” planted in the selection nursery in an early planting period (in 2020-2021)

Varietal samples	Harvesting time, day			Yield per plant, g	Yield, t/ha	Relative to standard,%
	60	70	80			
	Mean weight of tuber per plant, g					
“Sante” (st)	102	140	181	423	24,1	100,0
“Tashkent Ertagisi”	112	159	206	477	27,2	112,8
LSD 05					3,1	
Sx,%					2,8	

A dynamic analysis of the yield of the new “Tashkent Ertagi” variety and the

standard “Sante” potato variety planted in the early season was conducted with 60, 70, and 80-day intervals. The research results showed that the tuber weight of the “Tashkent Ertagi” variety increased by an average of 54 grams per plant compared to the standard variety, as observed at the 60-70-80 day intervals.

In the standard variant, the yield of the “Sante” variety was 24.1 tons per hectare, while in the new “Tashkent Ertagi” variety, this indicator was 27.2 tons per hectare, which is 12.8% higher than the standard variety.

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